

Needs and perspectives on the integration of generative artificial intelligence in Spanish educational context

Necesidades y perspectivas de la integración de la inteligencia artificial generativa en el contexto educativo español

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Abstract

This paper addresses the Delphi methodology by means of an expert panel for the detection of needs and perspectives on the integration of generative artificial intelligence tools. The results obtained after the last round indicate a high agreement among the different evaluators (Kendall's $W=,751$). The main concerns and needs detected are: the need to rethink teaching-learning and evaluation methods, the need to obtain training resources due to their scarcity, as well as the concern for fraud and the need for teachers to be trained. At the same time, the same questionnaire was passed to teachers and teachers in training, showing different perceptions from those of the experts.

Keywords

ChatGPT, Delphi, education, experts, perspectives.

Resumen

Este trabajo aborda la metodología Delphi mediante un panel de expertos para la detección de necesidades y perspectivas sobre la integración de herramientas de inteligencia artificial generativa. Los resultados obtenidos tras la última ronda indican un alto acuerdo entre los diferentes evaluadores (W de Kendall $\approx 0,751$). Las principales preocupaciones y necesidades detectadas son: la necesidad de replantear los métodos de enseñanza-aprendizaje y evaluación, la necesidad de obtener recursos formativos debido a su escasez, así como la preocupación por el fraude y la necesidad de formación del profesorado. Al mismo tiempo, se pasó el mismo cuestionario a profesores y profesores en formación, mostrando percepciones diferentes a las de los expertos.

Palabras clave

ChatGPT, Delphi, educación, expertos, perspectivas.

1. Theoretical background

The massive inclusion of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in higher education has marked a significant milestone in the democratization of learning (Atiaja-Atiaja & García Martínez, 2020).

The evolution towards web 3.0 and the increasing integration of multimedia technology have transformed educational environments, opening up new opportunities for knowledge acquisition (Rebollo-Catalán & Vico-Bosch, 2014). In this sense, the preparation and training of educators in the use of these generative technologies require a comprehensive approach addressing technological, pedagogical, and disciplinary aspects (Cózar, Zagalaz, & Sáez, 2015).

The emergence of generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) tools, such as ChatGPT for text and Dall-E for images, has had a substantial impact on higher education, sparking initial debates about their possibilities and potentialities (García-Peñalvo, 2023; Saz-Pérez & Pizà-Mir, 2024a). In this context, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a fundamental tool, especially in the field of machine learning, defined as the ability of machines to learn from experience and adapt their performance in unforeseen situations (Duan et al., 2019).

The lack of adequate preparation among educators to effectively utilize ICTs has been a recurring observation (Chai et al., 2010; Torres-Díaz & Infante-Moro, 2011). Similarly, their limited interest and participation in educational research projects have been evident (Pizà-Mir et al., 2023). This scenario becomes even more relevant when considering the widespread emergence of Gen AI, such as the launch of ChatGPT on November 30, 2022.

The effective integration of ICTs in the educational field has faced various challenges, both in their practical application in classrooms and in the training and performance of teaching staff. The evaluation of their impact on teaching and learning processes has been hindered by persistent pedagogical fragility (De Benito et al., 2017).

However, the use of ChatGPT in educational contexts has raised questions and has been subject to restrictions in some cases due to concerns about potential misuse by students (Herman, 2022; Marche, 2022; Stokel-Walker, 2022; Dwivedi et al., 2023;

Ropek, 2023; Meckler & Verma, 2022). Additionally, criticisms have been raised regarding errors and reasoning flaws in the responses provided by ChatGPT (Bowman, 2022; Llorens-Largo & ChatGPT, 2022).

Despite efforts to increase resources and measure technology usage, the need for continuous teacher training has been overlooked in educational policies (Fernández-Díaz & Calvo, 2012). This situation is further exacerbated in the university setting, where the adoption of ICTs in teaching and learning processes remains limited (Marcelo et al., 2015). This gap between technological promotion and teaching performance presents significant challenges in higher education (Cabero & Barroso, 2016; Sola et al., 2017; Suárez et al., 2013; Valdivieso & González, 2016; Mercader & Aldín, 2020; García-Peñalvo, 2023).

For all these reasons, it is essential to know the vision of experts in the field who are in direct contact with students in non-compulsory educational stages. The objective of this study is to determine the perspectives and needs for a correct integration of Gen AI tools in educational contexts.

2. Material and Methods

The experiment was carried out in two phases, a first phase using the Delphi method to seek consensus among different experts (Landeta, 1999; López Gómez, 2018). Three rounds of consultations (from general to more specific) were carried out for this purpose. For the second phase, to enrich the study, it was also decided to complement it with a questionnaire of teachers and teachers in training. This questionnaire was the same as the third round of the Delphi method, in order to compare the opinion and degree of agreement between two groups (experts and non-experts).

2.1. Participants

This study was divided into two phases of participant recruitment. First, a panel of experts (N=10) (Delbecq et al., 1975; Landeta, 2006; Akins, Tolson & Cole, 2005) was formed, of which 60% were men and 40% women. The call was made through dissemination through social networks and scientific forums of university and non-university teachers. To be part of the panel of experts, three (or more) of the following characteristics had to be accredited:

- *5 or more years of teaching experience (any stage)*
- *ICT coordination in educational centers*
- *Research experience: Projects and publications related to educational technology*
- *Teaching continuing learning courses and updating teachers in educational technology*
- *Higher education: Master or PhD in Educational Technology or similar*
- *Student of in-service training and refresher courses in educational technology, at least 100h (between one or more courses)*

Later, the third Delphi questionnaire was submitted and spreaded to find similarities and differences between the non-expert teachers and the expert panel. In this last phase, 120 people participated, of whom 47.5% were men, 51.6% women and one person answered another option (0.8%). Moreover, 40.8% had more than ten years of teaching experience, 22.5% between five and ten years teaching experience, 20.83% less than five and 15.9% were teachers in training (bachelor in education and teaching master degree).

2.2. Delphi Method

2.2.1. Initial Delphi Questionnaire: Design

An initial questionnaire (see Appendix A) was designed to gather the opinions and perspectives of experts in the educational field on the integration of Gen AI in teacher training and its implementation in the classroom.

2.2.2. The Second Round of the Delphi Method

The second round was designed with the purpose of refining and deepening the answers provided in the first questionnaire. This process contributes to building a stronger consensus around the specific issues addressed in the study.

- **Analysis of Previous Responses:** A thorough analysis of the responses provided by the experts in the first round of the Delphi study was conducted. Patterns, recurring themes, and divergences in responses were identified to inform the design of the second questionnaire.
- **Question Refinement:** The second questionnaire items were adjusted to address specific areas of disagreement or uncertainty identified in the first round.
- **More specific, closed-ended questions** were sought to facilitate convergence of opinions.
- **Distribution of the Revised Questionnaire:** The revised questionnaire was distributed to participants, accompanied by an anonymous summary, aggregating and synthesizing the responses from the first round.

2.2.3. Third Round of the Delphi Method

The third and final questionnaire was distributed to both, the panel of experts and to teachers and teacher trainees (non-experts) to compare the results of both groups. It was also disseminated through forums, seminars and social networks. A final analysis of the third round responses was conducted, highlighting areas of convergence (experts) and providing a clearer context on the views of the experts as well as non-experts.

2.3. Statistical Analysis

The statistical package Jamovi v2.3 (The Jamovi Project, 2022) based on R was used for data analysis. The analysis carried out for the concordance study between the different experts were correlation studies, descriptive studies (mean and standard

deviation, median values) and concordance analysis with Kendall's W (Kendall, 1939; Siegel, 1956). Kendall transformation offers approach to presenting ordinal data in a categorical format, allowing for the application of discrete methods and approaches. Unlike standard quantisation procedures that compromise precision, Kendall transformation accurately maintains the ranking while sacrificing the original distribution. Since Kendall's W is not a correlation coefficient, it can be transformed into a correlation coefficient (Spearman's r) to facilitate comparisons with other studies (Legendre, 2005).

3. Results and discussion

The results of this study are shown below. Appendix A shows which questions were asked in each of the three rounds of the Delphi method. The different tables show the number of reference items and in parentheses the number of questionnaires/round according to the Delphi methodology adopted.

3.1. First round of Delphi

The following table (Table 1) indicates the answers of the questionnaire's first round in order to refine the questions of the following rounds.

Table 1. Summary of the first questionnaire's answers that were used to develop the second questionnaire

item (q1)	Topic	Abstract of experts' answers
1	Professional Experience in Education and Technology	<i>Participants have varied experiences in education, including roles as teachers, trainers, and research projects, with a focus on educational technologies and virtual realities.</i>
2	Perception of Gen AI in the Educational Context	<i>Gen AI is perceived as a challenging and transformative tool, essential to strengthen critical and creative competencies, and its potential to radically change the objectives and methods of learning and content generation is highlighted.</i>
3	Current Needs of Teachers	<i>The need to adapt to educational changes, develop digital skills, creativity and critical thinking is highlighted. Training in the paradigm shift and ethical and technical understanding of Gen AI are key.</i>
4	Challenges for Effective Gen AI Implementation	<i>Changing negative perceptions, addressing data protection and family fears, managing copyright, overcoming resistance from senior faculty, and addressing the digital divide are key challenges.</i>

(continued)

Table 1. Summary of the first questionnaire's answers that were used to develop the second questionnaire (*continued*)

item (q1)	Topic	Abstract of experts' answers
5	Resources Needed to Support Teacher Training in Gen AI	<i>Contextualized training, ongoing seminars, collaboration with universities, courses for teachers and students, consultancy in Gen AI implementation, and rethinking pedagogical paradigms are required.</i>
6	Priority Areas for Teacher Education in Gen AI	<i>Priority areas include ethics in Gen AI, application in specific subjects, learning resources and assessment, and teaching-learning processes adapted to Gen AI.</i>
7	Successful Gen AI Implementation Experiences	<i>Successful experiences of some study participants highlight personalization of learning, development of critical and creative skills, and improvement of teaching processes in specific activities.</i>
8	Positive Impact of Gen AI on Learning	<i>The potential of Gen AI to generate meaningful, personalized, collaborative and autonomous learning is perceived, although some express skepticism about its actual impact at present.</i>
9	Ethical Concerns in the Use of Gen AI in Education	<i>The main ethical concerns center on data privacy, student data protection, authorship, reliability of sources, and potential ideological bias.</i>
10	Importance of Interdisciplinary Collaboration	<i>The importance of collaboration between teachers, technology developers, and educational experts for effective implementation of Gen AI is highlighted.</i>
11	Teacher Performance Evaluation in Gen AI Integration	<i>Teacher performance evaluation should be comprehensive, demonstrable with evidence, and focused on the actual impact on student learning.</i>
12	Suggestions for Educational Policies on Gen AI	<i>Educational policies that support the integration of Gen AI are proposed, including copyright legislation, support for teacher training and the promotion of collaborative practices, as well as pedagogical autonomy for teachers and centers.</i>
13	Institutional Support for Teachers in the Implementation of Gen AI	<i>The institutional support needed includes actual training, technological infrastructure, educational digital culture, coordination with universities, and rethinking pedagogical paradigms.</i>
14	Innovative Ideas to Improve Teacher Training in Gen AI	<i>Innovative ideas are proposed, such as interdisciplinary projects, tutoring chatbots for teachers, and the design of tools and protocols for formative evaluation.</i>
15	Expectations for the Future Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years	<i>Expectations for the next 5 years include a more dominant role for Gen AI, embedded in everyday devices, and its potential to personalize education and change educational paradigms at a dizzying pace.</i>

3.2. Second round of Delphi

Table 2 shows a summary of the answers obtained by the experts for those open-ended questions that do not correspond to those quantifiable on a Likert scale.

Table 2. Summary of the second questionnaire's answers that were used to develop the third questionnaire

item (q2)	Topic	Abstract of experts' answers
7	Successful Gen AI Implementation Experiences	<i>Diverse educational strategies with technology were explored, such as the creation of videopoems or the use of a ChatGPT to generate gamification activities, although they have not yet been implemented on a large scale in the classroom, highlighting the usefulness of Gen AI for work synthesis.</i>
11	Teacher Performance Evaluation in Gen AI Integration	<i>It is necessary to reconsider the evaluation systems in education, including methods such as the teaching portfolio, the comparison of productions with web resources, pre-test and post-test, and an educational inspection that accompanies the learning process and implementation of tools such as Gen AI, prioritizing the teacher's freedom in its integration and focusing on improvement measures, together with the implementation of new evaluation models and the use of learning and self-evaluation notebooks.</i>
12	Suggestions for Educational Policies on Gen AI	<i>It is necessary to focus on curricular changes to include Gen AI competencies, along with observance of existing legislation and educational policies focused on teacher training, funding for resources and methodologies, and free access to Gen AI tools and training, ensuring methodological flexibility and independent evaluation of learning.</i>
13	Institutional Support for Teachers in the Implementation of Gen AI:	<i>It is key to regularize the presence of Gen AI in education, focused on educational digital culture, teacher training, funding for resources and approaches, and effective practices that enhance learning, along with the creation of interdisciplinary teams and training resources in specific methodologies.</i>
14	Innovative Ideas to Improve Teacher Training in Gen AI	<i>The design of institutional Gen AI tools for planning and learning experiences is proposed, combined with practices such as peer observations, co-teaching, exchange events, development of resource banks and practical guides for teachers, noting the relevance of exploring the use of educational chatbots and establishing teaching pairs for their implementation in specific contexts.</i>
15	Expectations for the Future Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years:	<i>The concern resides in the gap between the evolution of society and education, while a technological revolution is on the horizon with Gen AI dominating the Internet. Adaptation to change and good use by teachers and students is expected, despite possible reluctance and deflation of the obsession with Gen AI.</i>

As can be seen in Table 3 (means, standard deviation and median) and Table 4 (concordance index using Kendall's W), it is observed that there is no concordance (Kendall, 1939; Siegel, 1956) among the respondents ($W = ,243$ and $r = ,16$). These low levels of concordance among the experts imply that a new round is needed to refine the framework in order to reach a consensus.

Table 3. Means and standard deviations of the group of experts for the items measured with Likert scale (second questionnaire)

	item1 (q2)	item2 (q2)	item3 (q2)	item8 (q2)	item10 (q2)
	Status Of Implementation	Thinking Skills Contribution	Ethical Comprehension	Learning Impact	Interdisciplinary Collaboration
M±SD	3,64±1,05	4,10±0,57	4,51±0,47	4±0,67	4,25±0,78
Median	Agree (4)	Agree (4)	Agree/Strongly agree (4,5)	Agree (4)	Agree (4)

Note: To check the complete statement, see appendix A.

Table 4. Agreement values according to Kendall's W for the group of experts for the items measured with Likert scale (second questionnaire)

Kendall's w				
W	r	χ²	df	p_value
,242	,16	9,7	4	,0455

It has been observed that ChatGPT, an artificial intelligence-based language model, exhibits the capability to generate false information, raising substantial concerns within the realm of academic integrity (Day, 2023; Mills et al., 2003). This ability poses significant questions regarding the reliability of information sources as the experts concern about (item9, q2, Table 5) and the necessity for rigorous scrutiny of tasks produced by Gen AI systems in school environments. The teacher resistant (item4, q2, table 5) was point as the main cause of resistance to implementation (Córica, 2020; Mercader, 2019).

Table 5. Percentage of responses for each item (hesitant, resources, priority training and worries), from the second questionnaire

	item4 (q2) (hesitant)	item5 (q2) (resources)	item6 (q2) (priority training)	item9 (q2) (worries)
Teacher resistant	80,00	Tech 80,00	Tech 50,00	Biases 40,00
Ethical concerns	70,00	Learning 90,00	Curricular 100	Ecol. footprint 10,00
Fraud	60,00	Financial 80,00	Ethical concerns 70,00	Reliability 70,00
				Data protection 70,00

Note: To check the complete statement, see appendix A.

3.3. Third round of Delphi

Tables 6 and 7 present the descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation and Kendall's W) respectively for the group of experts and the group of non-experts. Comparing the different items, it is observed that the means are systematically lower in the non-expert group, except for item 5 ("Resources Needed to Support Teacher Training in Gen AI: There are training resources and courses available to teachers through the educational administration on Gen AI"). A high concordance (Kendall, 1939; Siegel, 1956) is also observed in the responses of the group of experts, since they present a Kendall's W higher than ,75 and spearman's coefficient equal to ,72, respectively in the group of non-experts it is ,259 and ,25 (low concordance), and in both cases the values are significant observing the p_value of each of the samples ($p < 0.001^{***}$).

Table 6. Means and standard deviations of the group of experts and non-experts for the items measured with Likert scale (third questionnaire)

	item1 (q3)	item2 (q3)	item3 (q3)	item5 (q3)	item11 (q3)	item12 (q3)	item13 (q3)	item14 (q3)	item15 (q3)
	Need For Integration	Critical/Creative Thinking	Reformulation Of Tasks	Courses Available	Bureaucracy Help	Material Adaptation	Learning Changes	Teaching Changes	Fast Evolution
Expert	4,4	4	4,3	1,7	4,1	4	3,1	3,3	5
M±SD	±0,7	±0,67	±0,82	±0,67	±0,88	±0,47	±1,1	±1,06	±0
Median	Agree/Strongly agree (4,5)	Agree (4)	Agree/Strongly agree (4,5)	Disagree (2)	Agree (4)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)	Strongly agree (5)
Non-expert	2,93	2,59	3,82	2,42	3,23	3,67	2,49	2,80	4,43
M±SD	±1,38	±1,21	±1,28	±1,21	±1,35	±1,12	±1,14	±1,31	±0,92
Median	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Strongly agree (5)

Note: To check the complete statement, see appendix A.

Table 7. Agreement values according to Kendall's W for the group of experts and non-experts for the items measured with Likert scale (third questionnaire)

Subject	Kendall's W				
	W	r	χ^2	df	p_value
Expert	,751	,72	60,1	8	,0000000004***
Non-expert	,259	,25	253	8	,0000000000***

As observed in Table 6, there is a significant disparity regarding the necessity or not of integrating this type of tools, which may be related to the need to reformulate different tasks and teaching methods. The integration of Gen AI, especially represented by ChatGPT, has raised a series of ethical issues and challenges related to academic integrity in education (Arce, 2023; Han, 2023), as also seen in university students (Espinosa et al., 2023), since common tools like Turnitin are not capable of detecting whether these applications have been used.

Tables 8, 9 and 10 provide the percentage of each response (to be chosen from more than one option) on the components of the variables of the questions items that do not use a Likert scale. The aims of these questions are to determine which elements are necessary to be used in order to integrate Gen AI effectively in educational contexts.

Table 8. Percentage of responses for each item (hesitant and use), comparing the group of experts and non-experts from the third questionnaire

	item4 (q3) (hesitant)		item6 (q3) (use)	
	Expert	Non-expert	Expert	Non-expert
Retraining	60,00	41,67	Summarize	70,00 35,00
Cheating	70,00	56,67	Brainstorming	80,00 53,33
Misunderstanding	70,00	62,50	Audiovisual	30,00 49,17
			Adapted material	90,00 49,17

Note: To check the complete statement, see appendix A.

Table 9. Percentage of responses for each item (evaluation of implementation), comparing the group of experts and non-experts from the third questionnaire

	item7 (q3) (teaching)		item8 (q3) (learning)	
	Expert	Non-expert	Expert	Non-expert
School inspection	50,00	25,83	30,00	19,17
Experts	80,00	45,00	50,00	34,17
Non-implementation	-	34,17	-	34,17
Standardized tests	-	-	70,00	41,67

Note: To check the complete statement, see appendix A.

Table 10. Percentage of responses for each item (needs), comparing the group of experts and non-experts from the third questionnaire

	item9 (q3)		item10 (q3)	
	Expert	Non-expert	Expert	Non-expert
Training	80,00	70,83	Chatbots	60,00 22,50
Resources bank	90,00	53,33	User's guides	80,00 61,67
Legal counseling	60,00	52,50	Gen AI tools	90,00 62,50
Autonomy	50,00	53,33	Peer-to-peer	20,00 32,50
Standardized tests	30,00	30,00		
Free access	100,00	62,50		
Curricula modification	60,00	30,00		
Curricular orientation	90,00	42,50		
Financial	70,00	43,33		
Leave of absence	20,00	29,17		

Note: To check the complete statement, see appendix A.

Table 8 contains statements related to what respondents are hesitant to use them (item4), and the possible uses for them (item6). Table 9 refers to those third parties that should play a role in the evaluation of the way these tools are implemented (item 7) as well as the students' learning (item 8). Finally, Table 10, both item 9 and item 10 reflect the elements that participants perceive should be considered in order to be considered for the possible effective implementation of specific resources and strategies in the classrooms.

The lack of preparation in ICTs of teachers (Chai et al., 2010; Torres-Díaz & Infante-Moro, 2011) was pointed out as one of the main needs for a successful implementation of Gen AI (Table 8) but not as principal as fear of fraud or mere ignorance of possible uses being more important for that resistance to use it.

In addition to this issue, ChatGPT has proven to be an effective tool for providing personalized support to students from diverse educational communities and contexts (Baltazar, 2023; Gachago et al., 2023). The studies of Saz-Pérez and Pizà-Mir (2024b) concerning the way students use AI tools and the possibility of approaching new methodologies and didactic strategies for school tasks should also be highlighted. The model's ability to adapt and generate specific responses according to individual students' needs has been widely acknowledged, making it a valuable tool for inclusive education as the experts pointed (item6, q3, Table 8).

Lastly, it is worth noting that recent research, such as that conducted by Bahroun et al. (2023), has extensively explored the integration of Gen AI in educational settings. These studies provide a deeper understanding of the possibilities and

challenges associated with the implementation of Gen AI systems in the educational domain, thereby contributing to the advancement of knowledge in this emerging field.

Ethics in the implementation of ChatGPT in education is a significant concern (Crawford et al., 2023) with fraud, data protection and reliability of sources as main worries noted by the experts (Table 5). The necessity of strong leadership conducted by experts in evaluating tools and learning processes has been emphasized to ensure ethical use of Gen AI in education, addressing issues related to character, assessment, and learning through the use of Gen AI (Table 9).

In all cases, experts were more likely than non-experts to advocate a greater number of educational policies and/or institutional support for the use of Gen AI with the exception of those referring to greater autonomy encouraging educational leave. The same occurred when asked about innovative ideas to improve teacher education in Gen AI, where, with the exception of peer work, experts were more favorable than non-experts to implement more ideas.

On the one hand, for the successful implementation of Gen AI in educational context the experts think that it is mandatory to have training, a resources bank, curricular orientation and especially free access with a 100% agreement. On the other hand, leave of absence or standardized tests are not as important for the implementation for them.

In the same way, the experts consider a high relevance of the user's guides and Gen AI tools as innovative ideas to improve the teacher's training unlike peer-to-peer teaching work.

As shown in Table 11, participants (experts and non-experts) were given the opportunity to add comments to the answers if they were not reflected in the questionnaire on how the integration of Gen AI tools should be implemented.

Table 11. Other responses obtained by experts and non-experts at third questionnaire

Item 6: Successful Gen AI Implementation Experiences: Gen AI can be easily implemented in the classroom with

- *Proposal of collaborative Gen AI-Student constructions, critical and well-founded analysis of documents created with generative AI*
 - *Development of sessions, creation of videos, PowerPoint management*
 - *Gen AI increases productivity, that's good for work, not for learning.*
 - *I don't think it should be used in the classroom, at most it should be taught to students to use it correctly but not to encourage them to replace their own work with Gen AI, at least in ESO (secondary school).*
 - *All the options presented here are processes inherent to the teaching-learning process that students should carry out, except for the last two, in which I do not want to trust if they are equally effective as designing hands.*
-

(continued)

Table 11. Other responses obtained by experts and non-experts at third questionnaire (*continued*)

Item 7: Teacher Performance Evaluation in Gen AI Integration: Who should supervise the correct implementation?

- *Department heads and pedagogical/directive team*
 - *The same teachers. Like any evaluation.*
 - *The teacher themselves or the department.*
 - *No one. Every teacher already knows what they have to do if they use a tool.*
 - *Orientation Department and Board*
 - *It should be supervised by the teacher who implements it.*
 - *It's impossible to supervise.*
 - *The teacher themselves should have the knowledge and skills to self-assess their practice.*
 - *Evaluation by a group of experts (inspectors or not) who observe the classroom, Teachers of the same subject or area of study trained in Gen AI.*
 - *I don't think it should be supervised any more or less than any other Information and communications technology tool.*
 - *I believe evaluation should be integrated into the subjects.*
-

The customization of the learning process is a common thread in all of these studies. Su and Yang (2023) provide a strategic framework for the application of Gen AI, such as ChatGPT, in education, offering guidance on how to leverage the potential of this technology in diverse educational settings. Meanwhile, Kamalov et al. (2023) explore the new era of Gen AI in education and its sustainable impact, focusing on how technologies like ChatGPT are revolutionizing personalized learning approaches.

Furthermore, it has been noted that ChatGPT can be particularly beneficial for students with exceptional abilities, as its versatility allows it to address a wide range of topics and difficulty levels (Siegel, 2023). This capacity for adaptation and customization is essential for meeting the needs of a diverse group of students and fostering an educational environment that promotes holistic development.

4. Conclusions and prospectives

The development of this Delphi questionnaire in educational technology on Gen AI was supported by the concordance of responses among the experts consulted. In opposite to the same questionnaire does not report the same level of agreement among non-expert teachers in the field of educational technology, which shows a certain common criterion on the part of the experts on this irruption of Gen AI in educational contexts, but not on the part of the rest of the teaching staff.

Thus, the data obtained shows us a picture that agrees with previous literature and provides us with certain concreteness. The rapid evolution of Gen AI in educational contexts has been noted and there is a need for implementation in the eyes of experts, although they do not expect a radical change in the educational paradigm.

Educational policies for its implementation should focus on free resources, orientation and guidance. This implementation in the educational world should be carried out by specialists in the field using standardized material. To be successful, teachers should be trained and made aware of its potentialities such as help in the creation of materials to prepare lessons or adapted materials as well as its ethical risks such as data protection and the reliability of sources.

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Bibliographical references

- Akins, R. B., Tolson, H., & Cole, B. R. (2005). Stability of response characteristics of a Delphi panel: application of bootstrap data expansion. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 5(37). Recuperado de <http://goo.gl/nihfGc>
- Arce, D. D. (2023). Inteligencia artificial vs. Turnitin: Implicaciones para el plagio académico. *Revista Cognosis*, 8(1), 15-26.
- Atiaja Atiaja, L. N., & García Martínez, A. (2020). Los MOOC: Una alternativa para la formación continua. *Revista Científica*, 5(18), 120-136. <https://doi.org/10.29394/Scientific.issn.2542-2987.2020.5.18.6.120-136>
- Bahroun, Z., Anane, C., Ahmed, V., & Zacca, A. (2023). Transforming Education: A Comprehensive Review of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Educational Settings through Bibliometric and Content Analysis. *Sustainability*, 15(17), 12983. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151712983>
- Baltazar, C. (2023). Herramientas de IA aplicables a la Educación. *Technology Rain Journal*, 2(2), 15-15.
- Bowman, E. (2022, December 19th). A new AI chatbot might do your homework for you. But it's still not an A+ student. NPR. <http://bit.ly/3QL6z8A>
- Cabero, J., & Barroso, J. (2016). ICT teacher training: a view of the TPACK model / Formación del profesorado en TIC: una visión del modelo TPACK. *Cultura y Educación*, 28(3), 633-663. <http://doi.org/10.1080/11356405.2016.1203526>
- Chai, C. S., Koh, J. H. L., & Tsai, C. C. (2010). Facilitating preservice teachers' development of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK). *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 13(4), 63-73. <https://acortar.link/NvLDrb>
- Córica, J. L. (2020). Resistencia docente al cambio: Caracterización y estrategias para un problema no resuelto. *RIED. Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia*, 23(2), 255-272.

- Cózar, R., Zagalaz, J., & Sáez, J. M. (2015). Creating digital curricular contents of Social Sciences for Primary Education. A TPACK experience for future teachers. *Educatio Siglo XXI*, 33(3), 147-167. <https://doi.org/10.6018/j/240921>
- Crawford, J., Cowling, M., & Allen, K.-A. (2023). Leadership is needed for ethical ChatGPT: Character, assessment, and learning using artificial intelligence (AI). *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 20(3). <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.3.02>
- Day, T. (2023). A Preliminary Investigation of Fake Peer-Reviewed Citations and References Generated by ChatGPT. *The Professional Geographer*, 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00330124.2023.2190373>
- De Benito, B., Lizana, A., & Salinas, J. (2017). Using concept mapping for faculty development in the context of pedagogic frailty. *Knowledge Management & E-Learning*, 9(3), 329-347. <https://doi.org/10.34105/j.kmel.2017.09.020>
- Delbecq, A. L., Van de Ven, A. H., & Gustafson, D. H. (1975). Group techniques for program planning. Glenview, IL: Scott-Foresman and Co.
- Duan, Y., Edwards, J. S., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2019). Artificial intelligence for decision making in the era of Big Data-evolution, challenges and research agenda. *International journal of information management*, 48, 63-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.01.021>
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Kshetri, N., Hughes, L., Slade, E. L., Jeyaraj, A., Kar, A. K., ... & Wright, R. (2023). "So what if ChatGPT wrote it?" Multidisciplinary perspectives on opportunities, challenges and implications of generative conversational AI for research, practice and policy. *International Journal of Information Management*, 71, 102642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2023.102642>
- Espinosa, W. E. C., Bravo, V. B., Romero, M. E. Y., & Balarezo, C. E. B. (2023). Aplicaciones de la Inteligencia Artificial en la Preservación de la Originalidad y la Integridad Académica en estudiantes Universitarios. *Journal of Science and Research*, 7(2), 179-200.
- Fernández-Díaz, E., & Calvo, A. (2012). In-service teacher education in the innovatory use of ICT. An action research in Pre-school and Primary Education. *Profesorado. Revista de Currículum y Formación del Profesorado*, 16(2), 403-418. <https://acortar.link/x0R1kq>
- Gachago, D., Bali, M., & Pallitt, N. (2023). Equity-Oriented Learning Design: An Entangled Future. *Postdigital Science and Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-023-00420-w>
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2023). La percepción de la Inteligencia Artificial en contextos educativos tras el lanzamiento de ChatGPT: disrupción o pánico. *Education in the Knowledge Society (EKS)*, 24, e31279. <https://doi.org/10.14201/eks.31279>
- Han, H. (2023). Potential benefits of employing large language models in research in moral education and development. *Journal of Moral Education*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2023.2250570>

- Herman, D. (2022, December 9th). *The End of High-School English*. *The Atlantis*. <http://bit.ly/3Xhmle1>
- Kamalov, F., Calonge, D. S., & Gurrib, I. (2023). New Era of Artificial Intelligence in Education: Towards a Sustainable Multifaceted Revolution. *Sustainability*, 15(16), 12451. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151612451>
- Kendall, M. G., & Smith, B. B. (1939). The problem of m rankings. *The annals of mathematical statistics*, 10(3), 275-287.
- Landeta, J. (1999). *El método Delphi: una técnica de previsión para la incertidumbre*. Ariel.
- Landeta, J. (2006). Current validity of the Delphi method in social sciences. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 73(5), 467-482.
- Legendre, P. (2005). Species associations: the Kendall coefficient of concordance revisited. *Journal of agricultural, biological, and environmental statistics*, 10(2), 226-245.
- Llorens-Largo, F., & ChatGPT. (2022, 22 de diciembre). *Cavilaciones invernales*. Universidad. <http://bit.ly/3XGk0Jn>
- López Gómez, E. (2018). El método Delphi en la investigación actual en educación: una revisión teórica y metodológica. *Educación XXI: revista de la Facultad de Educación*, 17-40. <https://doi.org/10.5944/educxx1.20169>
- Marcelo, C., Yot, C., & Mayor, C. (2015). Enseñar con tecnologías digitales en la Universidad. *Comunicar*, 45, 117-124. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C45-2015-12>
- Marche, S. (2022, December 6th). *The College Essay Is Dead. Nobody is prepared for how AI will transform aca-demia*. *The Atlantis*. <http://bit.ly/3iEoPEd>
- Meckler, L., & Verma, P. (2022). *Teachers are on alert for inevitable cheating after the release of ChatGPT*. The Washington Post. Available at: <https://www.washingtonpost.com/education/2022/12/28/chatbot-cheating-ai-chatbotgpt-teachers>
- Mercader, C. (2019). Las resistencias del profesorado universitario a la utilización de las tecnologías digitales. *Aula Abierta*, 48(2), 167-174. <https://doi.org/10.17811/rifie.48.2.2019.167-174>
- Mercader, C., & Aldín, J. (2020). University teachers' perception of barriers to the use of digital technologies: the importance of the academic discipline. *International Journal of Educational Technology in higher Education*, 17(4), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-0182-x>
- Mills, A., Bali, M., & Eaton, L. (2023). How do we respond to generative AI in education? Open educational practices give us a framework for an ongoing process. *Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching*, 6(1), 16-30. <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2023.6.1.34>

- Pizà-Mir, B., Moreno-Vecino, B., & Monserrat-Monserrat, M.-V. (2023). Interest of non-university teachers in educational research projects. *REIRE Revista d'Innovació i Recerca En Educació*, 16(2), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1344/reire.42438>
- Rebollo-Catalán, A., & Vico-Bosch, A. (2014). El apoyo social percibido como factor de inclusión digital de las mujeres de entorno rural en las redes sociales virtuales. *Comunicar*, 43(22), 173-180. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C432014-17>
- Ropek, L. (2023, January 4th). *New York City Schools Ban ChatGPT to Head Off a Cheating Epidemic*. Gizmodo. <http://bit.ly/3kp8Ha9>
- Saz-Pérez, F., & Pizà-Mir, B. (2024a). Desafiando el estado del arte en el uso de ChatGPT en educación en el año 2023. *REIRE Revista d'Innovació i Recerca en Educació*, 17(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1344/reire.44018>
- Saz-Pérez, F., & Pizà-Mir, B. (2024b, February 2). Estudio exploratorio sobre usos y adaptaciones de las tareas escolares ante la irrupción de software de inteligencia artificial generativa. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/hmw69>
- Siegel, S. (1956). *Nonparametric statistics for the behavioral sciences* (No. 519.5 S54).
- Siegle, D. (2023). A Role for ChatGPT and AI in Gifted Education. *Gifted Child Today*, 46(3), 211-219. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10762175231168443>
- Sola, T., Nniya, M., Moreno, A., & Romero, J. J. (2017). Valoración del profesorado de educación secundaria de la ciudad de Tetuán sobre la formación en TIC desarrollada desde el Ministerio de Educación nacional. *Píxel-bit. Revista de Medios y Educación*, (50), 49-63. <https://doi.org/10.12795/pixelbit.2017.i50.03>
- Stokel-Walker, C. (2022, December 9th). AI bot ChatGPT writes smart essays – should professors worry? *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-04397-7>
- Su, J., & Yang, W. (2023). Unlocking the Power of ChatGPT: A Framework for Applying Generative AI in Education. *ECNU Review of Education*, 6(3), 355-366. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20965311231168423>
- Suárez, J., Almerich, G., Gargallo, B., & Aliaga, F. (2013). Las competencias del profesorado en TIC: estructura básica. *Educación XX1*, 16(1), 39-62. <https://doi.org/10.5944/educxx1.16.1.716>
- The Jamovi project (2022). *Jamovi. (Version 2.3)[Computer Software]*. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>
- Torres-díaz, J. C. & Infante-Moro, A. (2011). Digital divide in universities: Internet use in Ecuadorian universities. *Comunicar*, 19(37), 81-88. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C37-2011-02-08>
- Valdivieso, T., & González, M. A. (2016). Competencia digital docente: ¿dónde estamos? Perfil del docente de educación primaria y secundaria. El caso de Ecuador. *Píxel-Bit. Revista de Medios y Educación*, (49), 57-73. <https://doi.org/10.12795/pixelbit.2016.i49.04>

Biografia

Fabio Saz-Pérez: Degree in Biology and Biochemistry, with two Masters in Neurosciences and Teacher Training. With more than 10 years of teaching experience in secondary education, covering various scientific subjects, and 6 years of ICT coordination. Currently, he is a government worker for the Conselleria d'Educació de les Illes Balears. In the academic-research field, he is a PhD student in Educational Technology and has participated in projects for the introduction of new technologies in the classroom, as well as in congresses on ICT and science didactics. He is also a speaker in trainings related to neuroeducation.

Bartolomé Pizà-Mir: Degree and PhD in Science, also PhD in Education Sciences from the University of the Balearic Islands. With more than 10 years of teaching experience in compulsory and post-compulsory stages. In the field of research, he is the author of several publications (articles and book chapters) on evaluation, curriculum design and specific didactics of science and mathematics. He has been a speaker at several conferences related to these topics. Currently, he is also a university professor in the areas mentioned above and a teaching career official in the specialty of mathematics.

Appendix A

First questionnaire (q1)

1. Professional Experience in Education and Technology: Brief description of your experience in education, highlighting roles as a teacher, trainer, or in educational technology.
2. Perception of Gen AI in the Educational Context: How do you define generative artificial intelligence in the educational context?
3. Current Needs of Teachers: What do you think are the most pressing needs of teachers in relation to the integration of generative artificial intelligence in their educational practices?
4. Challenges for Effective Gen AI Implementation: What do you consider to be the greatest challenges for the effective implementation of Gen AI in the classroom?
5. Resources Needed to Support Teacher Training in AI: What resources (technological, financial, training, etc.) do you think are essential to support teacher training in Gen AI?
6. Priority Areas for Teacher Education in Gen AI: What specific areas should be prioritized in teacher training programs related to Gen AI?
7. Successful Gen AI Implementation Experiences: Can you share any successful experiences or best practices related to the implementation of Gen AI in the educational environment?
8. Positive Impact of Gen AI on Learning: How do you think Gen AI can positively impact student learning?
9. Ethical Concerns in the Use of Gen AI in Education: What ethical concerns do you see as most relevant to the use of Gen AI in education?

10. Importance of Interdisciplinary Collaboration: How do you see the importance of collaboration between teachers, technology developers, and educational experts to effectively implement Gen AI?
11. Teacher Performance Evaluation in Gen AI Integration: How should teachers' performance in integrating Gen AI in the classroom be evaluated?
12. Suggestions for Educational Policies on Gen AI: What educational policies do you think could effectively support the integration of Gen AI in education?
13. Institutional Support for Teachers in the Implementation of Gen AI: What type of institutional support do you think would be most beneficial for teachers who wish to implement Gen AI?
14. Innovative Ideas to Improve Teacher Training in Gen AI: Do you have any innovative ideas or suggestions for improving teacher education in relation to Gen AI?
15. Expectations for the Future Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years: What are your expectations for the role of Gen AI in education in the next 5 years?

Second questionnaire (q2)

1. Professional Experience in Education and Technology: Statement: On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is "No Integration" and 5 is "Full Integration", how well have you integrated Gen AI into your research projects or educational environment?
2. Perception of Gen AI in the Educational Context: On a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate Gen AI as a tool to strengthen critical and creative thinking in the educational context and content generation?
3. Current Needs of Teachers: Indicate to what extent you consider that digital skills, creativity and critical thinking are necessary for the effective integration of the Gen AI. Use a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is "Not Necessary at all" and 5 is "Very Necessary".
4. Challenges to Effective Gen AI Implementation: point out the challenges you consider most critical to Gen AI implementation. You may select up to three options: Faculty Resistance, Digital Divide, Ethical Concerns, Intellectual Property, Other (specify).
5. Resources Needed to Support Teacher Training in AI: List, in your opinion, the three most essential resources to support Gen AI teacher education: 1) Technological Resources, 2) Financial Resources, 3) Training Resources, 4 Other (specify).
6. Priority Areas for Teacher Training in Gen AI: Select the two specific areas that you consider to be the highest priority for teacher training in relation to Gen AI: 1) Technical skills development, 2) Curriculum integration, 3) Ethics and privacy, 4) Other (specify).
7. Successful Gen AI Implementation Experiences: Can you share a successful experience or best practice related to the implementation of Gen AI in the educational environment?

8. Positive Impact of Gen AI on Learning: On a scale of 1 to 5, how do you think Gen AI can positively impact student learning?"
9. Ethical Concerns in the Use of Gen AI in Education: List the two ethical concerns that you consider most relevant to the use of Gen AI in education: 1) Data protection, 2) Bias and discrimination, 3) Authorship and reliability of sources, 4) Other (specify).
10. Importance of Interdisciplinary Collaboration: On a scale of 1 to 5, how do you see the importance of collaboration between teachers, technology developers, and education experts to effectively implement Gen AI?
11. Teacher Performance Evaluation in Gen AI Integration: How should teacher performance in integrating Gen AI in the classroom be evaluated? What concrete measures would you propose?"
12. Suggestions for Educational Policies on Gen AI: Provide three suggestions for educational policies that you believe could effectively support the integration of Gen AI in education.
13. Institutional Support for Teachers in Implementing Gen AI: What type of institutional support do you think would be most beneficial for teachers who wish to implement Gen AI?
14. Innovative Ideas for Improving Teacher Education in Gen AI: Do you have any innovative ideas or concrete suggestions/proposals for improving teacher education in relation to Gen AI?
15. Expectations for the Future Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years: Share your expectations for the role of Gen AI in education in the next 5 years.

Third questionnaire (q3)

1. Professional Experience in Education and Technology: Do you consider it necessary to implement practices with Gen AI in your classroom?
2. Perception of Gen AI in the Educational Context: Gen AI contributes to critical and creative thinking
3. Current Needs of Teachers: Educational tasks and practices must be reformulated due to the irruption of Gen AI available to students
4. Challenges for the Effective Implementation of Gen AI: What do you consider to be the main cause of teacher resistance to the use of Gen AI? You can choose more than one, even provide another option": Need for retraining; Possible cheating by students; Misunderstanding of their use and applications
5. Resources Needed to Support Teacher Training in Gen AI: There are training resources and courses available to teachers through the educational administration on Gen AI
6. Successful Gen AI Implementation Experiences: Gen AI can be easily implemented in the classroom with: You can choose more than one, even bring in another option": Summarize and provide indexes and abstracts of long texts for their comprehension; Brainstorming on a topic before starting to work on it; Development of audiovisual material to enrich students' assignments or to supplement the teacher's materials; Development of materials adapted to the needs of teachers and learners.

7. Teacher Performance Evaluation in Gen AI Integration: In the case of implementing Gen AI in schools, who should supervise the correct implementation? You can choose more than one, including providing another option": School inspection (at the governmental level) or school management/headmaster team; Evaluation by a group of experts (inspectors or not) who observe the classroom.
8. Teacher Performance Evaluation in Gen AI Integration: In the case of implementing Gen AI in schools, how should student learning be monitored? You can choose more than one, including providing another option": School inspection (at the governmental level) or school management/headmaster team; Evaluation by a group of experts (inspectors or not) who observe the classroom; External or standardized learning tests.
9. Suggestions for Educational Policies on Gen AI: Select the policies/actions to consider for a possible effective implementation of these tools in the educational system. You can choose more than one, even contribute another option": Theoretical and practical training; Updated resource bank; Legal counseling; Methodological autonomy of teachers; Learning evaluation through independent tests; Free access to a variety of Gen AI tools; Modification of the curricula to adapt and concretize Gen AI skills; Curricular orientation; Financial resources; Paid leave of absence for training purposes
10. Innovative Ideas to Improve Teacher Training in Gen AI: Educational chatbots; Guides for use in specific educational areas or contexts; Specific institutional IA tools for the development of programs and learning environments; Peer observation and collaborative teaching.
11. Expectations for the Future of Gen AI's Role in Education in the Next 5 Years: Gen AI will help in the bureaucracy of teaching performance
12. Expectations for the Future of the Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years: Gen AI will help in the generation of teaching content and activities (teaching materials)
13. Expectations for the Future of the Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years: There will be a radical change in the way teachers TEACH
14. Expectations for the Future of the Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years: There will be a radical change in the way students LEARN
15. Expectations for the Future of the Role of Gen AI in Education in the Next 5 Years: The evolution of Gen AI is moving much faster than its teaching approach.